

SUPPLEMENTARY FILE: RESEARCH INSTRUMENT (QUESTIONNAIRE WITH SCORING GUIDE)

This document contains the complete validated Mpox questionnaire administered to participants, followed by the detailed scoring guide for each section. It serves as the full research instrument for transparency and reproducibility purposes.

PART I: FULL QUESTIONNAIRE (As Administered to Participants)

Knowledge Gaps and Predictors of Mpox Awareness Among Undergraduate Health Sciences Students in Ghana: A Cross-Sectional Study

Socio-demographics

1. Gender: Male Female
2. Age:
3. Marital status: Single Married Cohabiting Widow Widower
4. Programme of study: Nursing PA Public Health Pharmacy
5. Year of study: Two Three
6. Residency: Living in university accommodation Living in private accommodation Living with family
7. Type of occupancy: Single Double More than two
8. Have you had any clinical practice/internship in any health facility as a student? Yes No
9. How many times have you gone for clinical practice? At least Once At least Twice At least Thrice
10. Have you had any infectious disease during your clinical practice? Yes No

Section A: Knowledge of Monkeypox

1. Have you heard about Monkeypox? Yes No
2. From which source did you hear about Monkeypox? **Select all that apply**
College Tutor Social media TV/ Radio Healthcare worker Family or friends Research articles
3. Is Monkeypox new to you? Yes No I do not know
4. Are vaccines readily available to prevent Monkeypox infections? Yes No I do not know
5. Is Monkeypox curable? Yes No I do not know

Aetiology

1. What do you think causes Monkeypox? Bacteria Fungi Virus Parasite
2. Are Monkeypox and Chickenpox caused by the same agent? Yes No I do not know
3. Are Monkeypox and Smallpox caused by the same agent? Yes No I do not know
4. Is Monkeypox a myth (do not exist)? Yes No I do not know
5. Is Monkeypox highly contagious? Yes No I do not know

Mode of transmission

1. Monkeypox can be transmitted to humans through which of the following? *Select all that apply*
 - A. Blood or bodily fluid of an infected person
 - B. Direct skin-to-skin contact with the bodily fluid of an infected person
 - C. Droplet infection
 - D. Mother-to-child
 - E. Deep kissing and sexual intercourse with an infected person
 - F. Contaminated needles
 - G. Contaminated material such as clothing, bedding, and towels
2. Which of the following are at risk of getting Monkeypox?
 - A. Person who plays with monkeys
 - B. Hunters
 - C. Zoo keepers
 - D. Zoo visitors/tourist
 - E. Nurses
3. Animal-to-human transmission of Monkeypox occurs through the following means
 - A. From bites or scratches of an infected animal
 - B. During activities such as hunting
 - C. Skinning of wild animal/game
 - D. Playing with carcasses
 - E. Eating animals

One Health Concept

1. Do you think the African rope squirrel is a potential reservoir of monkeypox? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
2. Is Monkeypox endemic in rainforest areas of West and Central Africa? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
3. Can Monkeypox spread to any animal or cluster of animals presenting with a rash? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
4. Can Monkeypox be prevented by avoiding contact with wild or domestic animals? Yes [] No [] I do not know []

Epidemiology

1. What type of disease is Monkeypox? Physiological [] Deficiency [] Hereditary [] Infectious []
2. Has any case of Monkeypox been confirmed in Ghana? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
3. Is Monkeypox endemic in forested areas of Central and Western Africa? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
4. Has any Monkeypox case been confirmed outside Africa? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
5. Are females the most affected by Monkeypox? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
6. Can someone with Monkeypox also have another sexually transmissible infection such as herpes? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
7. Has there been a global outbreak of Monkeypox? Yes [] No [] I do not know []

8. Does Monkeypox affect people of African descent only? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
9. Has Monkeypox been found in temperate climates? Yes [] No [] I do not know []

Signs and symptoms

1. Are flu-like symptoms the initial symptoms of monkeypox? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
2. Is the Incubation period for Monkeypox between 5-21 days? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
3. Can skin lesions occur in monkeypox patients? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
4. Do individuals with monkeypox experience painful rash, enlarged lymph nodes, and fever? Yes []
No [] I do not know []
5. Does the monkeypox rash begin on the face and spread over the body, extending to the palms of the hands and soles of the feet? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
6. Does disease progression in monkeypox patients include the formation of macules, papules, vesicles, and pustules? Yes [] No [] I do not know []
7. Is Monkeypox itchy? Yes [] No [] I do not know []

Prevention

1. What can be done to prevent Monkeypox?
A. childhood vaccination against chickenpox will protect one against Monkeypox
Yes [] No [] I do not know []
B. suspected monkeypox cases should be isolated Yes [] No [] I do not know []
C. Proper hand washing with soap and water Yes [] No [] I do not know []
D. Should disposable gloves be worn to avoid direct contact with lesions
Yes [] No [] I do not know []
E. healthcare workers should wear appropriate personal protective equipment to prevent
Monkeypox Yes [] No [] I do not know []
F. Proper disinfection and cleaning of surfaces and equipment prevent the spread of
Monkeypox Yes [] No [] I do not know []

Section B: Perception of Human Monkeypox

1. I believe Monkeypox is a serious public health threat. Strongly Agree [] Agree [] Neutral []
Disagree [] Strongly Disagree []
2. I am worried about the possibility of contracting Monkeypox during my clinical training. Strongly
Agree [] Agree [] Neutral [] Disagree [] Strongly Disagree []
3. I believe I am adequately informed about how to protect myself from Monkeypox. Strongly Agree []
Agree [] Neutral [] Disagree [] Strongly Disagree []
4. I believe Monkeypox can be effectively prevented through proper hygiene and protective measures.
Strongly Agree [] Agree [] Neutral [] Disagree [] Strongly Disagree []

5. I would feel comfortable caring for a patient with suspected Monkeypox if proper protection is available. Strongly Agree [] Agree [] Neutral [] Disagree [] Strongly Disagree []

6. I think the general public is sufficiently aware of Monkeypox. Strongly Agree [] Agree [] Neutral [] Disagree [] Strongly Disagree []

7. I believe the university has adequately prepared students for emerging infections like Monkeypox. Strongly Agree [] Agree [] Neutral [] Disagree [] Strongly Disagree []

PART II: SCORING GUIDE FOR THE RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

QUESTIONNAIRE WITH SCORING GUIDE

Mpox Knowledge and Perceptions Among Undergraduate Health Sciences Students at Central University, Ghana: A Cross-Sectional Study

This version of the validated Mpox survey instrument includes the full scoring guide for each knowledge and perception variable. Each item is objectively scored based on the correctness of responses. Knowledge items are scored as 1 for correct responses and 0 for incorrect or 'I do not know' responses. Perception items are scored using a 5-point Likert scale as indicated.

Section A: Socio-demographics (Not Scored)

This section collects background information about the participants such as gender, age, programme of study, and prior clinical experience. It is not included in the scoring.

Section B: Knowledge of Monkeypox (Total Maximum Score = 51)

Each correct answer scores 1 point. Incorrect or 'I do not know' responses score 0 points. For multi-response items, each correct option scores 1 point unless otherwise indicated.

General Knowledge of Monkeypox (Max = 4 points)

1. Have you heard about Monkeypox? Yes = 1, No = 0
2. Source of information — descriptive only (not scored)
3. Is Monkeypox new to you? No = 1, Yes/I do not know = 0
4. Are vaccines readily available? No = 1, Yes/I do not know = 0
5. Is Monkeypox curable? Yes = 1, No/I do not know = 0

Aetiology (Max = 5 points)

1. Cause: Virus = 1
2. Monkeypox and Chickenpox same agent? No = 1
3. Monkeypox and Smallpox same agent? No = 1
4. Is Monkeypox a myth? No = 1
5. Is Monkeypox highly contagious? Yes = 1

Mode of Transmission (Max = 16 points)

1. Transmission routes: A, B, C, D, E, F, G correct (7 points)
2. At-risk groups: A, B, C, E correct (4 points); D incorrect
3. Animal-to-human transmission: A, B, C, D, E correct (5 points)

One Health Concept (Max = 4 points)

- 1. African rope squirrel reservoir? Yes = 1
- 2. Endemic in rainforest areas of West/Central Africa? Yes = 1
- 3. Can spread to animals with rash? Yes = 1
- 4. Prevented by avoiding contact with animals? Yes = 1

Epidemiology (Max = 9 points)

- 1. Type of disease: Infectious = 1
- 2. Case confirmed in Ghana? Yes = 1
- 3. Endemic in West/Central Africa? Yes = 1
- 4. Case confirmed outside Africa? Yes = 1
- 5. Females most affected? No = 1
- 6. Co-infection with STI possible? Yes = 1
- 7. Global outbreak occurred? Yes = 1
- 8. Affects Africans only? No = 1
- 9. Found in temperate climates? Yes = 1

Signs and Symptoms (Max = 7 points)

- 1. Flu-like symptoms initial? Yes = 1
- 2. Incubation period 5–21 days? Yes = 1
- 3. Skin lesions occur? Yes = 1
- 4. Painful rash with lymphadenopathy and fever? Yes = 1
- 5. Rash starts on face and spreads? Yes = 1
- 6. Disease progression macules→papules→vesicles→pustules? Yes = 1
- 7. Monkeypox itchy? Yes = 1

Prevention (Max = 6 points)

- 1. Childhood vaccination protects? No = 1
- 2. Suspected cases isolated? Yes = 1
- 3. Proper handwashing? Yes = 1
- 4. Disposable gloves? Yes = 1
- 5. Healthcare workers use PPE? Yes = 1
- 6. Disinfection of surfaces/equipment? Yes = 1

Knowledge and perception Scoring

Domain	Total Points	Cut-off	Classification
Knowledge	51	≥ 31 ($\geq 60\%$)	High knowledge
		< 31 ($< 60\%$)	Low knowledge
Perception	35	≥ 21 ($\geq 60\%$)	Positive perception
		< 21 ($< 60\%$)	Negative perception